

URBANIZATION DUE TO MIGRATION: A DISTRICT LEVEL ANALYSIS OF MIGRANTS FROM DIFFERENT DISTANCES FOR THE RAJASTHAN STATE

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Discussions:

Inter-state migrants share in total migrants is lagging in the state as compared to national scenario. Proportion of migrants settling in urban areas is on the rising side since last three decades however, its impact in different distances is varied. Urbanization rate due to migration is lower for intra-district migrants than to state, it is moderately high for inter-district migrants and just double for the inter-state migrants and this trend was evident for last three census periods.

Comparison of district level Urbanization rate is also skewed as on one side there are districts like Kota, Bhilwara, Jodhpur and Jaipur for which the migrant's urbanization rate has been phenomenal high than to state whereas for many districts like Jalore, Sirohi, Tonk, Karauli, Sawai Madohur etc it is very low and this difference also varies for intra-district, inter-district and inter-state migrants. Urbanization rate for Inter-state and inter-district migrants are higher for majority of districts where as for intra-district migrants it low for most of the districts.

Introduction: People migrate to different distances and there migration is governed by different reasons. Distance of place of migration plays an important role in the migration process and an analysis based on the remoteness of the origin and destination will reveal the push and pull factors in more explicit way. However, a common phenomenon is that people do migrate to a longer distance with a more focused objective and there propensity to settle in urban areas is always higher than the small distance migration.

Census data gives details of Intra-district, Inter-districts and Inter-states number of migrants and these three categories are considered to understand the inter-relationship of distance of migration and urbanization.

State vis-à-vis National Scenario:

Migration rate (% of migrants to total population) for the Rajasthan state is in line of country migration level of around 27%. State exhibited different track on account of migration distance. At national level 60.44% of migrants were in the intra-district, 25.67% in inter-district and 14.29% in inter state categories of migrants as compared to 65.45% intra district, 23.62% inter-district and 10.92% inter-state migrant in Rajasthan. Thus the share of intra-district migrants in total migrants is higher in the Rajasthan State as compared to Country level while it is on lower side for the inter state from the country level in the inter state category.

Migration Distance and Urbanization:

The migrant's contribution in urbanization is on the rising over the decades as 16.4%, 22.4% and 25.4% of the total migrants in the Rajasthan settled in urban areas during the period 1971-80, 1981-1990 and 1991-2000. This trend is also witnessed irrespective of the distance of migration. Migrants from different distances contribute in urbanization differently. For intra-district migration (Short Distance Migration) the urbanization due to migration inched to 13.5% in the duration 1981-90 from 10.1% in 1971-80 and further scaled to 15.2% in 1991-2000. Inter-district migration (Medium Distance Migration) contribution in urbanization advanced from 28.5% to 37.2% & 37.2% to 38.2% in this same duration and, similarly, Inter-state migration (Long Distance Migration) contribution in urbanization advanced from 36.5% to 44.4% & 44.4% to 46.7% in these three consecutive decadal periods.

Looking at the urbanization due to migrants from these different places (intra-district, inter-district and inter-state) it is found that share of inter-state migrants in urbanization is way ahead to share of inter-district and intra-district migrants in urbanization, as in the duration 1991-2000, 46.75% of interstate migrants settled in urban areas as compared to 38.2% and 15.2% of inter-district and intra-districts migrants in urban areas and similar trend were also observed in 1971-80 & 1981-90 durations. Not only inter-

state migration share in urbanization dominated but also its dominance is going stronger than inter-district and intra-district migration. Similarly the inter-district migration has an edge over the intra-district migration as far as urbanization is analyzed.

Share of urbanization due to migration in last three decades is considered to examine a trend in migrants in urban areas. Share of migrants in urbanization at state level and district level is compared for three consecutive decadal periods to establish the pattern in urbanization at the state and district level. For the above stated comparison six categories as given below are formed:

Category	Description
1	Higher During all the three decades
2	Higher during 1991-2000 & 1981-91 but lower in 1971-80
3	Higher during 1991-2001 but lower in last two decades
4	Lower During all the three decades
5	Lower during 1991-2000 & 1981-90 but higher in 1971-80
6	Lower during 1991-2000 but higher in 1981-90 & 1971-80

Districts falling in different categories exhibit a different trend as category 1 consist those districts, which observed higher urbanization from migration than the state level for three consecutive decadal period where as category 2 & 3 are having districts that performed better as far urbanization due to migration is concerned in last two decades and one decade respectively as compared to state level urbanization.

Category 3, 4 & 5 contain districts that have performed low in urbanization from state level in last three, two and recent decade respectively.

Cat. 1	Cat. 2	Cat. 3	Cat. 4	Cat. 5	Cat. 6
Intra District Migration					
Hanumangarh, Jhunjhunu, Churu, Bharatpur, Dholpur, Jaipur, Ajmer, Bhilwara, Kota, Pali	Alwar, Sawai madhopur, Baran.	Bundi, Jhalawar	Bikaner, Karauli, Dausa, Nagaur, Jodhpur, Jaisalmer, Barmer, Jalore, Sirohi, Tonk, Rajsamand, Udaipur, Bansawara, Dungarpur, Chittorgarh.		Ganganagar, Sikar,
Inter District Migration					
Jaipur, Jodhpur, Sirohi, Ajmer, Udaipur, Kota	Bhilwara	Sawai madhopur, Chittorgarh,	Bikaner, Jhunjhunu, Churu, Alwar, Karauli, Bharatpur, Dholpur, Dausa, Sikar, Nagaur, Jaisalmer, Barmer, Jalore, Tonk, Bundi, Rajsamand, Baran, Bansawara, Dungarpur, Jhalawar	Hanumangarh, Ganganagar,	
Inter State Migration					
Bikaner, Jhunjhunu, Sawai madhopur, Jaipur, Jodhpur, Jaisalmer, Ajmer, Tonk, Bhilwara, Udaipur, Kota,			Ganganagar, Hanumangarh, Churu, Alwar, Bharatpur, Dholpur, Karauli, Sikar, Dausa, Nagaur, Barmer, Jalore, Sirohi, Bundi, Bansawara, Dungarpur, Chittorgarh, Baran, Jhalawar		Rajsamand,

Many districts are having a relationship in similar direction as far as share of urban in-migrants is concerned from different distances and they follow the trend in same direction for urbanization level due to migrants. There are districts like Jaipur & Kota where percentage contribution of urban migrants is far ahead of state urbanization due to migrants for intra & inter-districts and inter-state migration during the periods 1971-80, 1981-90 and 1991-2000. Contrary to this, there are districts where percentage contribution of urban migrants is lower than state urbanization due to migrants in intra & inter districts and inter-state migration in three consecutive decadal periods. As, Inter-state migrants are having considerably high share in urbanization in Jodhpur district and it is way ahead of state urbanization figure due to inter-state migrants though it is falling below to state urbanization due to intra-district migrants and marginal up than state urbanization share due to inter-district migrants.

Percentage Contribution of inter-state and inter-district migrants in urbanization is higher for the state than to districts namely Hanumangarh, Churu, Alwar, Bharatpur and Dholpur whereas percentage Contribution of Intra district migrants in urbanization is higher for these districts than to state. Percentage Contribution of intra-district migrants in urbanization for Udaipur district is lower than state urbanization by intra-district migrants whereas for inter-district and inter-state migrants it is differing and contribution of inter-district and inter-state migrants in urbanization is higher for Udaipur than to state figure in three consecutive decades.

Therefore districts has shown a considerable variability in terms of migration contributing in urbanization when compared to state urbanization due to migration and this volatility is visible across different type of migrants whether inter-district, intra-district or inter-state migrants.

Intra-District Migration: Ten districts observed higher urbanization share of intra-district migration than state figures of 25.3% in 1991-200, 22.4% in 1981-90 and 16.4% in 1971-80. While two districts improved in migrant's urbanization than states urban migrants share in the period 1991-2000 though it was low than state share in year 1971-80 & 1981-90 and three

districts excelled the state urbanization level of migrants in the year 1981-90 and maintained it during 1991-2000.

Fifteen districts witnessed a lower share of urbanization due to migrants as compared to state level urbanization due to migrants whereas no district is classified in category 5, where share of urbanization in migrants don't witnessed downward trend in the two successive decadal periods i.e Lower during 1991-2000 & 1981-90 but higher in 1971-80. However Ganganagar & Sikar looked urbanization share of migrants lower than state share during 1991-2000 though higher in 1981-90 & 1971-80. Around half of the districts falls in categories 1 to 3 which consists the district that has performed well than the state as far as urbanization due to migrants is concerned.

Kota is having 13.6 percentage point more intra-district urban migrants than the % share of inter-district migrants of the state settled in urban areas followed by Ajmer with 8.8 more percentage points. At state level, 10.1, 13.5 & 15.2% of intra-district migrants are contributing to urbanization during 1991-2000, 1981-90 & 1971-80 period whereas Kota is having 28.8,29.1 & 22% of inter-district migrants settled in urban areas followed by Ajmer 23.4,22.4 & 17.5%; Bharatpur 26.8,22.5 & 17% in this same duration.

On the other side, Barmer with 5.1,5.3 & 3% of intra-district migrants settling in urban areas in the 1991-2000, 1981-90 & 1971-80 period followed by Jalore, Dungarpur & Bansawara were the district viewed the lowest intra-district migrants contributing in urbanization.

Inter-District Migration: There are 20 districts having inter-district migrants share in urbanization lower than the state figures of urbanization by inter-district migrants which is 38.4% in 1991-2000, 37.2% in 1981-90 and 28.6% in 1971-80. Urbanization by inter-district migrants gave that Ganganagar & Hanumangarh districts were having percentage share of inter-district urban migrants lower than state level share of inter-district urban migrants in the 1991-2000 & 1981-90 period though it was higher for these districts in 1971-80 duration. Six districts had better urbanization from inter-district migration than state.

Bhilwara improved the urbanization share in the inter-district migrants than to state in two consecutive period 1981-90 & 1991-2000 though it was low than state urbanization in migrants in the period 1971-80 whereas Hanumangarh, Sawaimadhopur & Chittorgarh improved the urbanization share in the inter district migrants than to state in period 1991-2000 though it was lower than state urbanization by inter-district migrants in the period 1981-90 & 1971-80. 71.5, 70.4 & 56.8% of inter-districts migrants having urban residence in Jaipur district during the period 1991-2000, 1981-90 & 1971-80 respectively. This urbanization share in inter district migrants, after Jaipur, is followed by Ajmer district with 52.5, 47.9 & 39%; Udaipur with 49.5, 42.8 & 32.3%; Bhilwara with 44.9, 41.8 & 28% and Jodhpur with 42.5, 39.0 & 29.9% in these durations. Therefore the urbanization by inter-district migrants has improved for these districts.

Jalore, Barmer, Nagaur, Sikar, Dausa, Karauli, Churu, Jhunjhunu & Alwar districts were having urbanization by inter district migrants 15 to 25 percent point higher than state share.

Inter-State Migration: There are only two categories of districts those have witnessed better urbanization by inter-state migrants than state share of urbanization from inter-state migrants over three consecutive decades and districts for which the urbanization share by inter state migrants remained down than to state urbanization by inter-state migrants over three consecutive decades except Rajsamand where urbanization in 1991-2000 has been lowered than state figures though it was higher in the duration 1981-90 & 1971-80.

There were 19 districts that observed the share of inter-state migrants residing in urban areas low to urbanization by inter-state migrants at state level whereas 11 districts witnessed reverse trend and there urbanization by inter-state migrants have been lowered than state figures in three successive decadal periods.

The leading districts having better urbanization by inter-state migrants in 1991-2000, 1981-90 and 1971-80 period are Kota (71.3, 79.7 & 81.3%)

Bhilwara (65.2,72.2,61.5%); Ajmer (84.4,87.6, 93.2%), Jodhpur (85.2,85.7, 86.8%) and Jaipur (87.7,89.7 & 86.2%).

Clearly the inter-state migrant's contribution in urbanization is fairly large share than any other distance migration like intra & inter-district migration share in urbanization. However the relative share of urban migrants in recent decades, in general, has gone down for these highly urban immigrants district.

Classification of Districts by Range of Percentage Share of Urban Migrants:

Districts for all the categories of migration (Intra & Inter-district and Inter-states migration) are classified in following categories where % of migrants attributing to urbanization in the census period 1971-80,1981-90 and 1991-2000 is (1) <20%, (2) 20-50% and (3) >50%. Result is summarized below:

Range of urbanization by migrants (in%)	Intra District			Inter Districts			Inter States		
	91-00	81-90	71-80	91-00	81-90	71-80	91-00	81-90	71-80
<20	22	25	31	2	4	11	4	5	5
20-50	9	6	0	27	27	20	19	15	14
>50	1	1	1	3	1	1	9	13	13

It is evident from above classification that there is stark variation in the urbanization by migrants in various categories. As number of districts are having >50% of urban migrants in total migrants are considerably high for migrants from other states and combining it with districts having 20-50% migrants it is found that eighty percent of districts fall in this class. For between district migrants most of the districts fall in the category where 20-

50% migrants are attributing to migration whereas it is quite contrary to within district migration and in this migration the urbanization share is very low.

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